

**AT THE CONFLUENCE OF THE WATERS OF THE SUS: AN EXPERIENCE OF CO-
MANAGEMENT IN MULTIPROFESSIONAL RESIDENCY**

EN LA CONFLUENCIA DE LAS AGUAS DEL SUS: UMA EXPERIENCIA DE COGESTIÓN EN UMA
RESIDENCIA MULTIPROFESIONAL

NA CONFLUÊNCIA DAS ÁGUAS DO SUS: UMA EXPERIÊNCIA DE COGESTÃO EM RESIDÊNCIA
MULTIPROFISSIONAL

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Manuscript submitted on: October 15, 2024.

Approved on: April 1, 2025.

Published on: June 23, 2025.

Abstract

The article is based on a preceptorship experience in a multidisciplinary residency in a Family Health Unit in Aracaju/SE, between February 2013 and February 2018. The objective of this report is to reflect, from the perspective of the preceptorship, on the co-management space in a multidisciplinary residency program and its contributions to the maintenance and improvement of the Unified Health System, through interprofessional work in conjunction with popular knowledge-making. The text describes the journey of the collective composed of residents, tutors and preceptors and the (trans)formations produced in the knowledge-making of workers in the Unified Health System: from a practice-based on the logic of professionalization/specialization to an interprofessional one; from the logic of the formal and institutionalized health network to a living network, as a space for meeting and belonging. Thus, the multidisciplinary residency is evaluated as collaborating in the expansion of knowledge and practices in Primary Health Care, in a collective process of (trans)formation of health care centered on the health needs of people in their territories, in learning together and from everyday life.

Keywords: Unified Health System; Public Health; Professional Training in Health; Interprofessional Education; Preceptorship.

Resumen

El artículo se basa en una experiencia de preceptoría de residencia multidisciplinaria en una Unidad de Salud de la Familia en Aracaju, Sergipe, entre febrero de 2013 y febrero de 2018. El objetivo de este informe es reflexionar, desde la perspectiva de la preceptoría, sobre el espacio de co-gestión en una

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residencia multidisciplinaria y sus contribuciones para el mantenimiento y mejoramiento del Sistema Único de Salud, a través del trabajo interprofesional en confluencia con el conocimiento popular. El texto describe el recorrido del colectivo compuesto por residentes, tutores y preceptores y las (trans)formaciones producidas en el conocimiento de los trabajadores en y dentro del Sistema Único de Salud: de una práctica basada en la lógica de la profesionalización/especialización a una interprofesional; de la lógica de la red de salud formal e institucionalizada a una red viva, como espacio de encuentro y pertenencia. Así, la residencia multidisciplinaria es evaluada como contribución para la ampliación de conocimientos y prácticas en Atención Primaria a la Salud, en un proceso colectivo de (trans)formación de la atención a la salud centrado en las necesidades de salud de las personas en sus territorios de vida, en el aprendizaje conjunto y desde lo cotidiano.

Palabras clave: Sistema Único de Salud; Salud Pública; Formación Profesional en Salud; Educación Interprofesional; Preceptoría.

Resumo

O artigo parte de uma experiência de preceptoria de residência multiprofissional em uma Unidade de Saúde da Família de Aracaju, Sergipe, entre fevereiro de 2013 e fevereiro de 2018. O objetivo deste relato é refletir, a partir do olhar da preceptoria, sobre o espaço de cogestão em uma residência multiprofissional e suas contribuições para a manutenção e melhoria do Sistema Único de Saúde, por meio do trabalho interprofissional em confluência com os fazeres-saberes populares. O texto descreve a caminhada do coletivo composto por residentes, tutoras e preceptoras e as (trans)formações produzidas no fazer-saber de trabalhadoras no e do Sistema Único de Saúde: de uma prática pautada na lógica da profissionalização/especialização para outra interprofissional; da lógica da rede formal e institucionalizada de saúde para uma rede viva, como espaço de encontro e de pertencimento. Assim, avalia-se a residência multiprofissional como colaborando para a ampliação de saberes e práticas na Atenção Primária à Saúde, em um processo coletivo de (trans)formação do fazer saúde centrado nas necessidades de saúde das pessoas em seus territórios vivos, no aprender junto e desde o cotidiano.

Palavras-chave: Sistema Único de Saúde; Saúde Coletiva; Formação Profissional em Saúde; Educação Interprofissional; Preceptoria.

Learning to unlearn

Working in healthcare within Brazil's Unified Health System (SUS) requires the (trans)formation of women workers⁴ so that they are able to learn to unlearn the established meanings, interpretations and ways of thinking that have been constituted and reproduced over time – and to recognize these differences within themselves and their own knowledge-practice (Paraíso, 2011). This (un)learning process enables a shift away from an individualizing,

⁴ It is worth noting that women make up 74% of the workforce, according to an article published on the Ministry of Health's website during the launch of the first workshop of the National Program for Equity of Gender, Race and the Recognition of Women Workers in the SUS. Available at: <https://www.gov.br/saude/pt-br/assuntos/noticias/2023/julho/ministerio-da-saude-realiza-primeira-oficina-do-programa-nacional-de-equidade-de-genero-raca-e-valorizacao-das-trabalhadoras-no-sus>. For this reason – and in light of the historical invisibility and devaluation of women's work, especially in care-related professions –, we have chosen to use the feminine form in our writing.

specialized and technician approach toward an expanded knowledge-practice; one that is shaped by collaborative interprofessional practices, connected and modulated in dialogue with popular and community knowledge and centered on the territorialized production of health. This means moving beyond a narrow focus on individual pathologies to develop practices rooted in the actual health needs of people within their living territories.

The Family Health Strategy (FHS) is the primary model for organizing Primary Health Care (PHC) within Brazil's Unified Health System. Through the reorganization of work processes within multiprofessional teams, the FHS aims to increase problem-solving capacity and contribute to the comprehensiveness of healthcare⁵. Despite the multiprofessional nature of both the SUS and the FHS, academic training continues to be fragmented, based on the exclusive roles of each professional discipline and marked by increasing specialization (Onocko-Campos; Emerich; Ricci, 2019). In this context, Multiprofessional Health Residency Programs (established by Law No. 11.129/2005) have emerged as a strategy to bridge the gap between technical training and the complex social issues that impact people's health and illness conditions.

Given the importance of reflecting on the role of in-service training, this text aims to shed light on the experience of (un)learning within the preceptorship of a multiprofessional residency program at a Family Health Unit (FHU) in the city of Aracaju, Sergipe, from February 2013 to February 2018. It also describes the collective process of building a shared learning journey among resident learners, a preceptor-learner, tutor-learners and coordinator-learners, and their contributions to the implementation and consolidation of interprofessionality within the FHS and the SUS.

The Multiprofessional Residency Program in Mental Health at the Federal University of Sergipe (REMU-SM/UFS) began in 2013. Between February 2013 and February 2018, REMU-SM/UFS underwent three coordination changes, expanded to include two additional professional categories and faced challenges such as the withdrawal of some preceptors and difficulties in recruiting new ones. Between 2013 and 2017, Aracaju was governed by a mayor affiliated with the Democratas (DEM) party, now known as União Brasil (UNIÃO), in an administration marked by neglect of the city and significant impacts on public health:

⁵ For more information, see Ordinance No. 2,436 of September 21, 2017, which establishes the National Primary Health Care Policy, as well as Consolidation Ordinance No. 2, also from 2017, available respectively at: https://bvsms.saude.gov.br/bvs/saudelegis/gm/2017/prt2436_22_09_2017.html and https://bvsms.saude.gov.br/bvs/saudelegis/gm/2017/prco002_03_10_2017.html#ANEXOXXII

interruption of garbage collection due to non-payment of the contracted company; delays in salary payments; lack of dialogue between managers and workers, leading to multiple strikes and work stoppages; precarious and fragile employment relations, with a lack of public service exams and stable hiring, and an increase in temporary selection processes; outsourcing of one of the Psychosocial Care Centers (CAPS); among other issues.

At the federal level, the country was undergoing a political crisis that began after the re-election of Dilma Rousseff, of the Workers' Party (PT), in 2014, and was later intensified by the 2016 coup (Silva; Benevides; Passos, 2017) that led to the president's removal from office. The 2018 election contributed to the militarization of the Ministry of Health (MH) and deliberately dismantled several health programs and policies, which resulted in the deterioration of various health indicators. Examples include a decline in vaccination coverage, an increase in maternal mortality – particularly among black women from peripheral areas – and the hospitalization of their babies due to severe malnutrition, the latter being a clear sign of the return of hunger and its consequences for early childhood (Chioro; Costa, 2023). Several successful policies were affected, among them PHC, which saw the publication of a new National Primary Health Care Policy (PNAB) in 2017 (Brasil, 2017). This occurred despite opposition from the National Health Council (NHC), which strongly objected to the changes – especially given the context of underfunding caused by Constitutional Amendment (CA) No. 95/2016 (Mitros et al., 2023)⁶.

Despite the context described, Family Health Teams (eSF) of Aracaju retained autonomy to engage in collective planning and to carry out activities and actions guided by the principles and guidelines established by the SUS, which were expected to be implemented through FHS. In this way, the FHU where this group – preceptor and residents – was based remained a space of strengthening and resistance in defense of the SUS, of democracy and of the collective construction of a model of care grounded in ideals of social transformation capable of addressing inequalities and inequities.

As previously mentioned, this text aims to reflect, through the lens of preceptorship, on an experience of co-management within a multiprofessional residency program and its contributions to health care in a Family Health Unit. It tells the story of a collective journey,

⁶ Constitutional Amendment (CA) No. 95, dated December 15, 2016, froze public investment in health and education for 20 years by establishing the New Fiscal Regime within the scope of the Federal Government's Fiscal and Social Security Budgets. Available at:
https://www.planalto.gov.br/ccivil_03/constituicao/emendas/emc/emc95.htm?ref=correiosabia.com.br

which, in a challenging and, at times, despairing local and national context, made the daily choice to build a counter-hegemonic mental health care project, one that would embrace “the complexity and multidimensionality of health needs” (Peduzzi, 2001, p. 107). This space of resistance was built through the planning and implementation of actions that blurred the boundaries between professional disciplines and, in this in-between space, knowledge, health practices and the shared creation of care strategies came together – strategies more aligned with local realities and, therefore, more effective.

In this (un)learning process carried along by the waters of the SUS, we now present the open channels of this collective flow, which this text offers as a space for reflection. We begin by discussing Primary Health Care and its priority strategy in Brazil: the Family Health Strategy. Next, we explore the co-management strategy within the SUS and its significance in fostering the autonomy of all those involved in the delivery and governance of health care. We then present the Multiprofessional Residency in Mental Health and its collective construction. Further on, we reflect on the need to move beyond multiprofessional teamwork toward true interprofessionality. Finally, we discuss the role of preceptorship and its contribution to the processes of training and co-management within the SUS – the central focus of this text.

Primary Health Care and the Family Health Strategy

Freire (2011) reminds us that the act of learning came before that of teaching, and that it was through social learning that we discovered teaching was possible. For him, learning implies openness to risk and adventure; to building, unbuilding and rebuilding. Experiencing Brazil’s Unified Health System as an FHS⁷ worker meant discovering and collectively constructing ways of doing-knowing health that do not disregard the social issues embedded in the lives that are both shaped by and shape the services. Combining this experience with preceptorship, a pedagogical practice that supports professional training (Onocko-Campos; Emerich; Ricci, 2019), allows for the emergence of a community of unlearning (Hooks, 2017, 2020), a space for shared reflection on the everyday realities of health work. This space calls

⁷ As this article is fundamentally composed of memory fragments from a preceptorship process within the Family Health Strategy (FHS) experienced by one of the authors, the writing will, at times, appear in the first-person singular.

upon the preceptor and students – whether undergraduates in internship positions or residents – to collectively think through strategies, arrangements and pathways toward a living, dialogical and expanded clinical practice. An expanded clinic is a theoretical and practical tool aimed at contributing to an approach to the health-illness-care process that considers the individual and their environment in all their uniqueness. It allows for confronting the fragmentation of knowledge and health actions (Brasil, 2013). From this perspective, we hold that one of the guiding threads of such an expansion lies precisely in interprofessional practice, especially when woven together with the living knowledge of the communities and territories to which the people we care for belong.

Primary Health Care in Brazil began its formal reorganization in 1991 with the creation of the Community Health Agents Program (PACS), which was community-oriented. This was followed by the Family Health Program (PSF) in 1994, which was later renamed the FHS. Both programs are considered the foundations of the PNAB, whose first version was published in 2006, with subsequent revisions in 2011 and 2017. From the beginning of the PSF, the eSF had a general practitioner, a nurse, a nursing technician and community health agents. Initially, each Family Health team was responsible for up to 4,500 individuals. However, this number was later reduced to a maximum of 4,000, with a recommended average of 3,000, depending on the degree of vulnerability of the families within the covered territory (Pinto; Giovanella, 2018). The PNAB defines that PHC within the SUS must offer:

[...] a set of individual, family and collective health actions involving health promotion, prevention, protection, diagnosis, treatment, rehabilitation, harm reduction, palliative care and health surveillance, carried out through integrated care practices and qualified management. These actions are delivered by multiprofessional teams and directed toward a defined population within a specific territory, for whom the teams assume health responsibility (Brasil, 2017).

Brazilian PHC has the Family Health Strategy as its priority approach and the preferred entry point into the Health Care Network (HCN)⁸. It must have high problem-solving capacity, clinical and caregiving skills and incorporate diagnostic and therapeutic technologies. The structure of the team working within the FHS emphasizes its multiprofessional nature, thus breaking away from the previously dominant hospital-and-physician-centered model that existed before the strategy was implemented in 1994. For this new logic to take shape in

⁸ The Health Care Network (HCN) consists of organizational arrangements made up of health actions and services with different technological configurations and care missions, articulated in a complementary and territory-based manner, and characterized by various attributes. Available at: https://bvsmms.saude.gov.br/bvs/saudelegis/gm/2017/prt2436_22_09_2017.html

practice, it is essential to have collective and ongoing spaces for planning, evaluation and training, in order to avoid the risk of reproducing a model of care focused solely on disease, rather than on the prevention of illness and the promotion of health.

The FHS is guided by principles and directives that organize and define the services provided. Its key directives (decentralization, regionalization, hierarchization and community participation) make it possible to work within a defined area (territorialization), allowing health teams to become familiar with the territory, including its challenges and potential. It also includes population assignment, which helps build bonds with the families and individuals served. Other PHC principles include: person-centered care, which supports the development of autonomy, trust and knowledge to make informed decisions about one's own care – thus enhancing the problem-solving capacity of this level of care; and the possibility and privilege of following individuals across their life course (continuity of care), helping to avoid loss of reference points and reducing the risk of harm caused by professionals unfamiliar with patients' life stories and previous treatments (Brazil, 2017).

To ensure the implementation of the principles of universality, comprehensiveness and equity in PHC, a key aspect lies in broadening professionals' perspectives to recognize the potential and opportunities in each local context. Universal and continuous access to PHC services means that health units must be organized in a way that they consistently welcome and receive all individuals who seek care, and that health teams are responsible for developing appropriate responses to the health needs presented, whether individual or collective. Comprehensive care involves two dimensions. One refers to the existence of services organized in health care networks, designed to meet health needs across different levels of complexity – including health promotion and maintenance, disease and injury prevention, treatment, rehabilitation, harm reduction and palliative care. The other dimension of comprehensiveness concerns the responsibility of PHC to recognize the social nature of illness and the biological, psychological, environmental and social needs of individuals and communities. Equity entails the understanding that the right to comprehensive and universal health care must acknowledge and respect diversity in beliefs, race, ethnicity, gender and any form of limitation, and promote the development of strategies to reduce inequalities, prevent discrimination and avoid the exclusion of individuals or groups (Brasil, 2017).

However, establishing multiprofessional teams through official ordinances alone does not guarantee that the actions developed will fulfill the principles and guidelines of the SUS⁹. Therefore, educational spaces that enable the formation of communities of unlearning (hooks, 2017, 2020) within practice settings in the SUS and the FHS are foundational for transforming professional practice toward comprehensive care – one that considers local specificities, territorial dynamics and the presence of specific, itinerant and dispersed populations. The inclusion of undergraduate and graduate students from the health field in the FHS is supported by the understanding that primary health units are potential spaces for education, professional training, teaching and research in practice and technological innovation and assessment for HCN.

Co-management, Multiprofessional Residency in Mental Health and the Family Health Strategy: the confluence of waters that (trans)form

The SUS' National Humanization Policy (HumanizaSUS) holds that there is no separation between care delivery and management practices, and that health is produced when all forms of knowledge are valued. The guiding principles of HumanizaSUS are co-responsibility, autonomy and the protagonism of all individuals involved in the health production process: care and management professionals, students and users of the system (Brasil, 2009).

Campos (2006), through the Paideia Method, proposes the expansion of individuals' autonomy in decision-making, which would contribute to the democratization of life and co-responsibility, reducing authoritarianism and hierarchical structures. For him, autonomy does not imply lack of commitment, but rather the enhancement of each person's or collective's ability to express desires, interests and opinions freely and, from there, to establish agreements and shared commitments (Campos, 2006). Sharing knowledge-practices, building a network where each member holds a relative power – recognized and legitimized by all – and where different interests, collectives and projects can coexist and complement each other: this is the idea of co-management inspired by Campos's Paideia Method (Guizardi; Cavalcanti, 2010), which we experienced and were shaped by in the Multiprofessional Residency in Mental Health, and upon which we reflect in this text.

⁹ For a more in-depth discussion on the principles and guidelines of the SUS, see Matta (2007).

The Professional Health Residency was created in 2005 through Law No. 11.129 of June 30, 2005, as a “*lato sensu* postgraduate training modality focused on education through service and aimed at professional categories within the health field, excluding medicine” (Brazil, 2005, art. 13), to be carried out under a full-time regime and under teaching-care supervision (*ibid.*). The Multiprofessional Residency in Health was created shortly afterward by Interministerial Ordinance No. 2.117 of November 3, 2005, which was later supplemented and amended by subsequent ordinances. The current format is governed by Interministerial Ordinance MEC/MS No. 16 of December 22, 2014 (Brazil, 2014), which defines it as a *lato sensu* education modality, characterizes it as education through service and establishes the shared responsibility of the education and health sectors, a 60-hour weekly workload, a minimum duration of two years and a full-time commitment regime.

The REMU-SM/UFS began in 2013, and the first group entered the SUS Aracaju's health services in February of that year. Initially, it included three professional categories – Nursing, Pharmacy and Psychology – with two residents from each category, divided into two groups. In 2016, the programs of Physical Education and Social Work were added. The initial practice settings were established through agreements with the Coordination of Psychosocial Care of the Sergipe State Health Secretariat (SES), the HCN of Aracaju, including two FHU and the Psychosocial Care Network (REAPS), encompassing all its services and programs, whether publicly managed or contracted. The residency program was also present in a setting internal to the Federal University of Sergipe (UFS), specifically the psychiatric ward of the University Hospital (HU).

In the following years, the SES management setting ceased to be a practice scenario, and the residency program remained only within the SUS Aracaju and the HU. The selection of the two FHU, out of the 43 existing at the time, was based on several factors, the main one being the profile and availability of the preceptors, who were invited and had the autonomy to accept or decline. One of the units had a referral team for outpatient mental health care, composed of a psychologist and a psychiatrist, who, according to the organization of HCN, treated users referred to by the family health teams of the linked units. The other FHU had a history of innovative experiences in matrix support¹⁰ in collaboration with the Psychosocial Care Center (CAPS) to which it was affiliated.

¹⁰ Matrix support is a way of producing health in which two or more teams jointly develop a pedagogical-therapeutic intervention proposal. Available at: https://bvsmms.saude.gov.br/bvs/publicacoes/guia_pratico_matriciamento_saudental.pdf

In Aracaju, student access to practice settings is mediated by the Permanent Health Education Center, which played a fundamental role in the development and qualification of pedagogical practice spaces within the SUS Aracaju's services. This was done through the mapping of practice scenarios, identifying potential professionals for preceptorship and building connections with educational institutions to discuss the pedagogical projects of each field. The presence of technical advisors for different levels of training (technical courses, undergraduate programs and residencies) contributed to the development of strategies and activities for sharing experiences developed by students within the services and for the qualification of the preceptorship space.

The Permanent Health Education Center maintained a registry of professionals available for preceptorship, containing information such as the type of students each professional could supervise (technical courses, undergraduate programs, PET-Saúde¹¹, residencies), their assigned service and available time slots. It is important to note that professionals serving as preceptors in the SUS Aracaju did not receive any financial compensation from either the municipality or the educational institutions – except in the case of PET-Saúde, where students, preceptors, tutors and coordinators received a stipend paid by the Ministry of Health. Additionally, the preceptorship role was not considered in the municipal health career progression process.

The REMU-SM/UFS had a technical advisor at the Permanent Health Education Center, who, together with faculty from UFS, formed the program's Structuring Teaching-Care Core. The initial placement of the six (6) residents in the services was organized by this core, based on a standard weekly schedule and the division of the group into two (2) teams, each including the three (3) professional categories. After three months, the teams would rotate scenarios. It's worth noting that the REAPS in Aracaju consists of one CAPSi, one CAPSiad, one CAPS III Alcohol and Other Drugs, three CAPS III, a Harm Reduction Program, fourteen mental health referral professionals within FHU, one Mental Health Outpatient Clinic, one Shelter Unit and three Therapeutic Residences, all supported by a mental health emergency service at São José Hospital. We register this composition to justify the decision to alternate resident placements

¹¹ The Education through Work Program for Health (PET-Health) is a joint initiative of the Ministry of Health and the Ministry of Education aimed at strengthening the integration between education, health services and the community. It seeks to enhance, through work-based learning, the knowledge of health professionals as well as undergraduate students in health-related programs. For more information, see: <https://www.gov.br/saude/pt-br/composicao/sgtes/pet-saude>

in different practice scenarios. The aim was to provide experience across multiple points in the network and along various lines of care (alcohol and other drugs, mental disorders, childhood and adolescence etc.), thus fostering a network-oriented perspective and practice – working with the network through the professional development provided by the residency.

The 2013 group arrived at the services without any initial welcoming activities and was received at each site by the respective preceptors. In this account, the residents were welcomed following the usual routine for individual students or student groups: after an initial meeting in the preceptor's office, we walked through the unit while introducing them to the structure and to professionals from the six (6) eSF. It's important to highlight that the unit had several preceptors, which facilitated a broad welcome for the residents. As was customary, the group was also introduced during the team meeting, held every Friday morning. Starting in 2014, the new students were welcomed by second-year residents (R2), who guided them through the practice settings. From 2015 onward, the orientation took a new format, involving a meeting held prior to the residents' integration into the practice scenarios. This will be detailed later in the text.

The process of shaping the REMU-SM/UFS training was a co-management experience from the very beginning, and it remained so throughout our time with the collective, from 2013 to 2018. The commitment to this shared management approach in institutional settings was inspired by Campos (2006) and his Paideia Method, which emphasizes that co-management is the responsibility of all and uses collective problem-analysis and decision-making spaces as its methodological foundation. In this way, it becomes possible to produce both healthcare and health training based on local work processes and specific realities, increasing autonomy and engagement through enhanced analytical and intervention capacities over one's world and oneself. Onocko-Campos, Emerich and Ricci (2019) also highlight the importance of establishing collective co-management spaces as strategies for training and strengthening students' capacity to maintain democratic practices in their work.

Following this path, the collective, composed of residents, preceptors, coordinators, tutors and the Permanent Health Education Center technical advisor, met monthly to establish and revisit agreements, plan activities and discuss issues related to the residency program. Occasionally, the format of these meetings changed depending on shifts in the

residency's coordination, as each new coordinator brought different perspectives and styles, but the monthly meeting frequency remained consistent. Decisions on the distribution of practice scenarios and the residents' weekly schedule were made within this space, based on the collective's evaluation of which scenarios should receive more or less time, and which should be scheduled during the first or second year, considering the level of complexity. The collective also chose themes for formative meetings with all residents, covering clinical cases or services such as Harm Reduction, Mental Health Practices in Primary Care, Alcohol and Drug Crisis Management, among others.

Initially, the standard weekly schedule for the residents was organized as follows: one group was assigned to the two FHU (with one shift in each), one adult CAPS (four shifts), the mental health emergency service (one shift), the University Hospital (two shifts) and theoretical activities (three shifts). The other group was allocated to the SES management (two shifts), one CAPSad (our shifts), the REAPS Aracaju management (one shift), the University Hospital (two shifts) and theoretical activities (three shifts). During the first semester of residency, the group evaluated that the standard weekly schedule involved too many practice settings. Due to the distinct and specific demands of each service or space, the learning process was compromised, as residents did not have enough time to understand the service's reality and develop care strategies, establish bonds with the technical team and service users etc.

As a result, changes were implemented from the second group onwards, including the reduction and redistribution of practice settings, the extension of the residents' stay in the FHS, with six months in each unit, and limiting each resident to only one type of CAPS per semester in the first year. Based on discussions within the management collective, it was decided that residents would complete three shifts per week for one semester in each FHU, along with three shifts in the CAPS unit linked to that FHU. This change, proposed by the preceptor affiliated with the FHS and accepted by the collective, allowed residents to explore opportunities for intersectoral actions, planned jointly with teams from the Social Assistance Reference Center (CRAS)¹² and professionals from local schools. It also fostered reflection on

¹² The Social Assistance Reference Center (CRAS) is the main point of entry into Brazil's Social Assistance system. It is a public facility, typically located in areas of greater social vulnerability, where social assistance services are offered with the goal of strengthening family and community bonds. For more information, see:

the importance of mental health promotion and prevention at the primary care level. In the second year, residents rotated through other services and programs, such as Harm Reduction, the child and adolescent CAPS (CAPSi) and the mental health emergency service, while maintaining contact with the FHS through coordination between services. This organization of practice settings remained in place from 2013 to 2018, the period covered by this report.

The change in the standard weekly schedule, particularly the increased time spent in the FHU, was essential for enhancing the REMU-SM/UFS residency program. It also highlighted the importance of viewing practice settings as communities where residents could also "unlearn"¹³ the asylum-based logic of care still present in many services and within us – a logic that seeks to isolate the mentally ill, to "CAPSulate" them, or, at best, to refer them to so-called "specialized" services. This care model is reinforced by the fact that health professional training still predominantly occurs in hospital environments or follows a hospital-centered, individualizing approach focused on already-established diseases. Such a framework significantly shapes the practices carried out in Primary Health Care (Belfort; Vasconcelos, 2019).

Thus, the ongoing challenge for PHC is to invest in transformations and the expansion of care. This is achieved through health education directed at both professionals and the people with whom we work in living territories, grounded in interdisciplinarity, intersectorality and a broadened clinical approach. Such a challenge requires weaving our professional practices together with popular knowledge and health needs that reflect both the problems and the potential of these territories. In other words, we are in the process of doing-thinking-sprouting a therapeutic model that does not place disease at its center – one that is built, negotiated and mobilized alongside the service user, their family, neighbors and other points of care¹⁴ beyond the boundaries of formal health services. We are creating health

<https://www.gov.br/mds/pt-br/acoes-e-programas/suas/unidades-de-atendimento/centro-de-referencia-de-assistencia-social-cras>

¹³ Inspired by bell hooks' (2017, 2020) concept of learning communities – which, in turn, is deeply rooted in Freirean thought – we are guided by an educational approach grounded in the exchange of knowledge and experiences, mobilizing affect between those who teach and those who learn. In this in-between guidance, a time-space of creation, preceptors and residents blend their roles in pedagogical experimentation, forming a territory of mutual learning. In this way, the educator/preceptor/professional is also strengthened and empowered by the process, by this community of unlearning.

¹⁴ Points of care are spaces where health services are provided, and all are equally important for achieving the objectives of the healthcare network. Examples of points of care include households, health units, specialty centers, among others. For more information, see:
https://bvsmms.saude.gov.br/bvs/publicacoes/modulo4_regulacao_redes_atencao_saude.pdf

practices not as something imposed by the system, as in hospital settings, but rather as something that emerges from our bodies, our ways of living, something that considers the person and “their relationships with family, with the territory where they live and circulate, with work” (Belfort; Vasconcelos, 2019, p. 61), and how all these elements affect and express their singular life, their health and their processes of illness. From the collective space of REMU-SM/UFS and more specifically from the perspective of preceptorship, we are analyzing and co-weaving, through interprofessional and community-based lenses, a model of mental health care within the FHS that includes all involved: professionals from health and other public policy sectors, as well as the communities with whom we work, together.

Multiprofessional Teams, Interprofessionalism and Preceptorship in Confluence with Living Territories and Popular Knowledge

The day you [...] learn that you do not know and are willing to learn Indigenous languages – instead of teaching them – as well as Indigenous architecture, the uses of plants from the caatinga, the sertão, the cerrado, the pantanal; the day you open yourself to learning the way we once learned from you, then there will be a confluence. A confluence of knowledge. [...]. A counter-colonization.”
(Nêgo Bispo/Antonio Santos, 2018, p. 09)

The organization of work in teams has a significant cost-effectiveness impact, as it facilitates population access to services, produces better outcomes, and generates greater professional satisfaction in daily work routines as well as among those receiving care. It can be said that professionals tend to work in teams when they perceive that the outcomes are more satisfactory and beneficial for users, their families, and the broader community (Peduzzi et al., 2018). The literature points to a lack of consensus on the fundamental aspects that define teamwork and its variations and prefixes – namely: multi-, inter- and trans-. These prefixes suggest:

a growing degree of interaction, integration and coordination among disciplines or professions, depending on the following term, disciplinary or professional, which refer, respectively, to the fields of knowledge or disciplines and to professional practices. (Peduzzi et al, 2018, p. 2)

In this context, we view this lack of consensus not simply as a problem, but rather as an opening for problematization, an invitation to prolong the question, rather than rushing to closure through quick, normative answers. It becomes an opening for the non-consensual

creation of a commons among heterogeneous elements; an opening that involves disciplines from distinct fields of knowledge, diverse professional practices and that also exceeds the confines of disciplines and professions traditionally defined and hierarchized as the “health sciences”, embracing popular practices and knowledges regarded as equally indispensable in the negotiation and co-production of health care. It is on such expansions of interprofessional practices, networked with popular practices, that we wish to reflect in this part of the text.

The increasing complexity of health needs related to population aging, the rise in chronic illnesses and conditions and the understanding that psychic suffering is ethical-political (i.e., the result of exacerbated social inequalities linked to class, race/ethnicity, gender, age and region) call for an expanded professional approach. This approach should enable an affective distribution, in the words of Krenak (2023, p. 64): “We need to have affection for existence, for the experience of life” – for the experiences of people and of the Earth in their living territories. We must engage, listen and respond to the harshness of the world not with more control, guardianship or violence, but with the tenderness of shared experience.

Perhaps then, we will be capable of changing how we feel and perceive – of opening our professional practices to movement and to the overflow of our professional cores and formal services, toward an encounter with the environment and the relationships that emerge precisely where people live. In this way, teamwork and the organization of the healthcare system in networks also demand an expanded notion of “network.”. The (dis)care of the formal (modern-colonial, white and hetero-cis-normative) healthcare, psychosocial and primary care networks – networks within which we are entangled and by which we have been shaped – can be transformed through a counter-colonial confluence between professional and popular knowledges (Santos, 2018). Through this, we may generate and exchange knowledge across professions and with territories, co-creating living and shared webs of health knowledge-practices.

Campos (2000), when reflecting on knowledge and its organization into practices, proposes the distinction between the professional core and the professional field. The core would demarcate “the identity of a knowledge area and of professional practice; the field, on the other hand, would be a space where each discipline and profession seeks support from others to fulfill its theoretical and practical tasks” (Campos, 2000, p. 220). He adds that core

and field are “mutable and mutually influence each other, with no precise boundaries being detectable between one and the other” (ibid., p. 221).

Ellery, Pontes and Loiola (2011) point out that the diversity of professional categories present in the FHS and their insertion in the territory contribute to the expansion of what would be considered the field of knowledge and practices. Faced with the complexity of health situations, professionals, when realizing they are not able to address them alone, turn to other categories and develop collaborative interprofessional practices, blurring the boundaries of what would constitute the disciplinary core. In doing so, what once belonged to the shared field becomes part of the everyday routine of these professionals, and is gradually incorporated into care: it is when a professional begins asking questions and seeking information they previously wouldn't have, and starts observing the socio-subjective dimensions that may impact health and illness processes – such as family eating habits, whether pets are vaccinated, identifying symptoms of dengue, elder care, situations of violence or even mapping formal and informal support networks, among others.

Multiprofessional teamwork happens collectively, where horizontal relationships are established between different professional categories and is configured “in the reciprocal relationship between technical interventions and the interactions of the multiple agents involved” (Peduzzi et al., 2018, pp. 7–8). This relationship must be based on reciprocity and dialogue: the more dialogical the interaction, the less fragmented and more holistic the resulting care. Beyond that, interprofessional teamwork creates the collective, a space-time of co-creation between individual and society, between knowledge and invention, a plane of forces capable of shifting constituted forms. To better understand this, we turn to the arguments of Lílíana da Escóssia: the “plane of forms” concerns the already constituted modes – whether individual or collective. “As collective forms, we can cite social groups, collectivities, society. The plane of forces is the plane where forms are constituted/created, [...] a plane of relationships (Veyne, 1982)” (Escóssia, 2009, p. 689). This plane is of the order of the collective, “a space of interstices. A plane of creation or co-creation of individual and social forms, the origin of all change, a plane of movement” (ibid.).

Considering the complexity of health-illness processes that the SUS users present, it becomes increasingly necessary for professionals to access and compose with knowledge beyond their disciplinary cores, to forge new ways of doing, new ways of caring in health and new conceptions of multiprofessional, networked work. However, these transformations

demand that professionals exercise dialogue as an everyday strategy to cope with the tensions that emerge during the shift from a technician and specialist-guided practice – still fragmented and grounded in the biomedical model – toward comprehensive care and toward health as both a value and a right (Pezuzzi et al., 2018), and as a creative process, the normative capacity to invent new norms for oneself in the face of the unreliability of the environment (Canguilhem, 1982).

In order for the articulation between professional categories to produce more resolute and comprehensive actions, such articulation must be intentional and collaborative, based on critical reflection about everyday experience. These actions must be capable of aggregating the knowledges of all professional cores, highlighting each one's potential (Arneemann et al., 2018) and the generative space of emerging practices that unfolds in the space-time between them, the space-time of the collective (Escóssia, 2009).

At this point, we wish to affirm: interprofessional teamwork can constitute a transformative space-time for conceptions and practices of health, and multiprofessional residency programs provide a space for interprofessional education. These programs foster integration among different professional categories, creating opportunities for the development of skills necessary for joint learning, collaborative planning and the collective execution of activities that address people's health needs in their territories. This transformative space-time finds in care its guiding thread.

Care, in this context, refers to the accompaniment of the genesis processes of both the self and the world, aimed at opening the communicational coefficient of individuals and groups, what Guattari (2004) called transversality. To analyze is to open up the forms of reality, increasing their quantum of transversality, attuning them to their genetic plane, placing side by side, through a relation of contiguity, the form of the phenomenon and the lines that compose it. It is to make visible that these lines traverse the forms and that forms are nothing more than arrangements of lines of force. (Passos; Eirado, 2015, p. 110)

Pezuzzi et al. (2018) point out that communication is fundamental to interprofessional collaboration and, consequently, to the implementation of care and health attention. It is essential to combine instrumental action (technical-scientific knowledge) with communicative action (which presupposes transversal communication among all involved subjects), in order to discern whether a brief listening with rapid information exchange is sufficient or whether it is necessary to access and integrate other forms of knowledge –

whether from one's professional core or from a shared field – in order to respond to the health needs that emerge in daily practice.

In the case of REMU-SM/UFS, it was observed that, upon arriving at PHC, most residents had little knowledge and/or experience with the SUS, the FHS, working in multiprofessional teams or with the logic of care oriented by the health needs of individuals, families and communities. Some undergraduate courses, depending on the choice of internships during training, did not provide any contact with the SUS, leaving the prevailing image of it as a deficient system marked by queues and low-quality care. I recall the statement of a Physical Education professional who shared that her only reference to the SUS was the health unit her grandfather visited to receive the medications he used. Given this context, the responsibility of the preceptor becomes even greater, especially in facilitating the residents' learning about the Sanitary and Psychiatric Reforms, the SUS, its ethical-political foundations, principles and guidelines, its organization in Care Networks, extended clinic and multiprofessional teamwork.

One of the strategies adopted to address the lack of knowledge about the SUS and its functioning as a space for professional training in the health field was the implementation, starting in 2015, of a Pedagogical Workshop prior to the placement of residents in health services. This initiative aimed to introduce the practice settings, the SUS Aracaju, the evaluation tools and to discuss and develop the profile of those involved in the REMU-SM/UFS process (residents, preceptors and tutors), as well as to present the syllabus of the disciplines and the guidelines for the preparation of the Residency Final Project. In 2017, the last group I followed, this initial activity was expanded and redefined, becoming the Pedagogical Welcoming Week of the Multiprofessional Residencies in Family Health and Mental Health, both offered by UFS. The week's program was collaboratively designed by residents, preceptors and Permanent Health Education Center staff. Activities included workshops and discussion circles on the SUS, the Sanitary Reform and the Psychiatric Reform; production of field diaries and portfolios; case studies; presentation, negotiation and agreement on the practice settings and the standard weekly schedule.

Upon arriving at the FHU, with the aim of fostering learning experiences, residents were encouraged by the preceptor to get to know the surrounding territory and its health needs. This was done in various ways: conversations with the preceptor and/or other team

members, observation of the health unit's operations, from the arrival of users to their service (reception, consultations, pharmacy, vaccination room etc.), guided visits to the unit's coverage area¹⁵ and population by ACS and shared consultations with the preceptor. Residents were also integrated into existing FHU activities, whether group, individual or intersectoral. Additionally, activity planning was done collectively among the residents and later discussed with the preceptor. The preceptor sought to foster an environment conducive to broadening perspectives within the field of knowledge and practice among diverse professional categories, understanding that the residency offers spaces for the critical analysis of health needs and, through this reflection, contributes to interprofessional education (Arnemann et al., 2018).

There are numerous benefits that the presence of residents brings to health service, and here we aim to reflect on some of them. One of the main advantages is the fresh perspective they bring, unburdened by the fatigue, habits and automatism that may affect long-standing workers in those spaces. Creativity, combined with reflective thinking stimulated by theoretical components, is a valuable asset to PHC. Onocko-Campos, Emerich, and Ricci (2019) point to the outsider's gaze and cite Nunes, Torrenté, and Prates (2015), who acknowledge the learner's potential to question and critically engage with a new social environment. One example was a mental health education activity conducted by residents with USF workers to discuss mental health care in PHC and the local mental health care flow. The strategy was developed after residents observed, during interactions with staff, a lack of knowledge and stigmatized views regarding mental health issues present in the territory, such as needs arising from alcohol and drug use, use of psychotropic medication and referral pathways within Aracaju's Health Care Network. These meetings were held biweekly, lasted one hour and included the participation of all professional categories during the first year of the REMU-SM/UFS.

¹⁵ The term "territory" refers to a unique geographic unit, constructed in a decentralized manner within the SUS framework for the implementation of strategic actions aimed at health surveillance, promotion, prevention, protection and recovery. The organization of the FHS involves the division and subdivision of territories and assigned populations and/or specific population groups, whose health care is the responsibility of the FHS. For more information, see: https://bvsmms.saude.gov.br/bvs/saudelegis/gm/2017/prt2436_22_09_2017.html. It is worth noting that the concept of territory employed in this text encompasses, but also transcends, this official formulation, as will be further elaborated below.

Residents were able to strengthen and enhance existing FHU activities, such as health education initiatives in a public elementary school affiliated with the School Health Program (PSE)¹⁶. The PSE had been implemented by the FHU since its inception in 2007, with joint planning between the school and the FHU. Topics for health education actions with students were based on the needs identified by health teams in the territory and the issues raised by teachers through classroom observations. The arrival of residents contributed to the inclusion of teachers and families in these actions, after it became evident during planning meetings that both groups faced challenges dealing with students/children who had learning or behavioral difficulties. This led to discussion circles with teachers on mental health conditions, including presentations of services available within Aracaju's Health Care Network. In partnership with the Popular Health Movement of Sergipe (MOPS/SE), a morning session was also held featuring Integrative and Complementary Practices (PICS)¹⁷ such as meditation, relaxation, auriculotherapy, reiki, massage therapy and medicinal plants. Another initiative involved discussion circles with families on mental health in childhood and adolescence.

As previously mentioned, a key challenge was the development of multiprofessional work skills and competencies among residents. Residents were placed in practice settings in groups composed of different professional categories included in the residency program, which meant they had to work with individuals from other fields – often complete strangers – throughout the week. Additionally, the dynamics of the services required collective planning of actions and activities. Considering that health education still tends to be fragmented and focused on the core of each profession, with little to no experience in multiprofessional teams, the guidance and support of the preceptor was crucial in building this experience.

¹⁶ Considering that PHC is responsible for the entire population within its territory – including the school community – the School Health Program (PSE) is an intersectoral policy between the Health and Education sectors that aims to provide comprehensive health care for students through actions focused on prevention, health promotion, and care. For more information, see: <https://www.gov.br/saude/pt-br/composicao/saps/pse>

¹⁷ Integrative and Complementary Health Practices (PICS) are therapeutic approaches that emphasize compassionate listening, the building of therapeutic bonds and the connection between human beings, the environment and society. For more information on PICS within the SUS, see: <https://www.gov.br/saude/pt-br/composicao/saps/pics>

To support residents' integration into the FHS and reduce the stress potentially caused by insecurity and unfamiliarity with the service and its dynamics, we established a routine: at the end of each shift, and later at the end of each week, we would conduct a review of the day or the week. This reflection included discussions on the preceptor, the setting, other staff members and the planned and implemented activities. This space served not only as guidance for the residents but also as a place for shared learning. Thus, the residency preceptorship itself was also a (trans)formative process, one that recognized and encouraged the residents' autonomy, knowledge, and proposals.

Preceptorship in the FHS: currents of (un)learning and belonging

Despite serious setbacks, there have been – and will continue to be - radical and constructive changes in the way we teach and learn, as minds “seeking freedom” teach us to transgress and to transform.
(bell hooks, 2020, p.59)

Reflecting on the experience of preceptorship within the REMU-SM/UFS and its contribution to overcoming the multiprofessional mandate in favor of an interprofessional work logic (Onocko-Campos; Emerich; Ricci, 2019), a shift from the multi to the inter (Peduzzi et al., 2018), requires an understanding of the collective journey undertaken by preceptors, residents, tutors and coordinators. It also involves highlighting the construction of transversal, dialogical and welcoming relationships, filled with “disobedient languages” (Ceccim et al., 2024, p. 8805), which contributed to the building of a community of unlearning¹⁸ shaped by interprofessionality.

The actions planned and implemented within the USF valued technical-scientific knowledge while, at the same time, aiming, through the complexity and multidimensionality of health needs, to foster communication and collaboration across different professional categories, including both residents and service professionals, as well as with popular and community-based health knowledge and practices. Strategies such as workshops, co-management discussion circles, intersectoral actions and in-depth knowledge of and within the territory, all rooted in reflection on the everyday life of health services and in the creation of extended health networks, contributed to a collective practice that brought together diverse forms of knowledge and experience.

¹⁸ Starting, as previously mentioned, from bell hooks' (2000) concept of a learning community.

The preceptorship space is always a challenge for health professionals, and countless questions arise. With each new group, it becomes necessary to build mutual trust. Preceptorship is thus (de)constructed through the (re)composition of health practices, by sharing the difficulties experienced by students, whether residents or undergraduates, upon arriving at the USF, as well as the difficulties voiced by professionals at the USF who, with the arrival of new practitioners, found opportunities to renew their own practices. The relationships among residency colleagues and with USF professionals provoke movements within and among us, inviting all involved to take up the position of learner-workers, co-creating the SUS and, through it, co-constructing their professions. Within the SUS, we come to understand the limits of technical-scientific-specialist knowledge and move beyond it by constructing a shared territory of collective knowledge. Together, we strive to overcome fragmented academic training, not by devaluing the theoretical and technical reflection it offers, but by expanding it through experimentation in living territories and through the richness of the co-managed space of the multiprofessional residency, of multiprofessional teams and of a shared SUS made by each and every one of us.

In this sense, preceptorship can support the emergence of confidence in the resident's still-developing technical competence (Onocko-Campos; Emerich; Ricci, 2019) because the preceptor has already occupied this place of uncertainty when facing the new and knows that this confidence will be shaken many times in the future, an ongoing process of learning/unlearning a collective practice not confined to professional cores, one that blurs the boundaries between core and field. The preceptor-resident relationship also contributes to broadening the resident's perspective on numerous social issues that are often absent from professional training. There, on the ground of the SUS, at its gateway, the primary health care units, residents learn that health is the result of collective living conditions and that illness processes are effects of social inequalities. To reach this expanded understanding of care centered on the health needs of individuals within their territories, in all their complexity and multidimensionality, requires a willingness to act together.

This means practicing collaboratively, interprofessionally and interdisciplinarily, and also engaging in intersectoral actions with policies such as education and social assistance, something that the space of preceptorship can also nurture. Yet, there is a special ingredient

in this journey of expanding health care: the meeting of interprofessional and intersectoral collaborative practice with popular health practices, those created by people in their living territories, which broadens our understanding of health networks, recognizing that they are not only made up of formal, institutional structures.

Health practice is a continuous process of learning-unlearning, composing-decomposing, something that unfolds in daily life when we give it the time it needs: “time to fix our gaze on the small, on what we are not used to seeing” (Olegario, 2015, p. 376); time to “make way for experiences, to open breaches where new encounters may settle in” (ibid.). Any and all (trans)formation of practices and knowledges begins with what unsettles, what affects, what mobilizes. In the waters of (un)learning, of (de)composing and (trans)forming, knowledge-practice in the SUS reinvents and strengthens itself through encounters between residents, preceptors and community, within a living network of interdisciplinary and popular care that grows with each encounter, each touch, each person who arrives, like waters flowing into other waters. Waters that together form a current, breaking through the confines of technical-scientific knowledge, daring to artfully activate disobedient voices and languages within living, convergent and processual territories, space-times of the waters that call us to meet.

In the SUS Aracaju, a city shaped by the confluence of rivers that meet and reach the sea, we are slowly learning that to produce health is to produce life; and “to produce life is to enter a flow, to be a current, it is to belong, not to be isolated” (Krenak, 2023, p. 67). Flowing with these waters, despite serious setbacks, there has been and will continue to be a current of radical (trans)formations in the way we teach and learn to produce health and life. REMU-SM/UFS made possible this confluence of professionals, practice settings and lives which, like the rivers of Ará¹⁹ meet, expand and change as they move toward the sea. Each and every one was (trans)formed and contributed to the (trans)formation of many others – then, and in future waters. “When you share knowledge, knowledge only grows. It’s like converging waters. When one river meets another, it doesn’t cease to be a river, it becomes a greater river” (Nêgo Bispo, 2022²⁰).

¹⁹ “Ará” is a loving nickname for Aracaju, used by those who were born in or live in the city.

²⁰ Trajetórias, Itaú Cultural, in Nego Bispo – Trajetórias (<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Tqt9BnrolFg>). Accessed on March 10, 2025.

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